

Child Abuse Neglect in the Media

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Introduction

Abuse and neglect is defined as “injury, sexual abuse, sexual exploitation, negligent treatment or maltreatment of a child”. It must be circumstances that indicate that the child’s health, welfare, and safety is harmed. While the injury inflicted upon a child may be instantly available, it can have result in lasting trauma that is both physical and psychological. The impact of this trauma is experienced not only by the child, but also by other children, families, and society.

It is also not possible to define the specific kind of abuse, as it can be simultaneously physical, psychological, behavioural, and societal terms in its impact.

Signs of child abuse

The presence of child abuse and neglect can be assessed with the following signs: The child: “shows sudden changes in behaviour or school performance; has not received help for physical or medical problems brought to the parents’ attention; has learning problems (or difficulty concentrating) that cannot be attributed to specific physical or psychological causes; is always watchful, as though preparing for something bad to happen; lacks adult supervision; is overly compliant, passive, or withdrawn; comes to school or other activities early, stays late, and does not want to go home.”

Risk Factors of Abuse and Neglect

Most child abuse occurs within the family. Risk factors include parental depression or other mental health issues, a parental history of childhood abuse, and domestic violence.

Child neglect and other forms of maltreatment are also more common in families living in poverty and among parents who are teenagers or who abuse drugs or alcohol. More children are abused by a caregiver or someone they know, than abused outside of the home by a stranger.

Child neglect can include physical neglect (failing to provide food, clothing, shelter, or other physical necessities), emotional neglect (failing to provide love, comfort, or affection), or medical neglect (failing to provide needed medical care). Psychological or emotional abuse results from all of the above, but also can be associated with verbal abuse, which can harm a child’s self-worth or emotional well-being.

Signs and Symptoms

It is not always easy to recognize when a child has been abused. Children who have been maltreated are often afraid to tell anyone, because they think they will be blamed or that no one will believe them. Sometimes they remain quiet because the person who abused them is someone they love very much, or because of fear, or both.

Parents also tend to overlook signs and symptoms of abuse, because they don't want to face the truth. This is a serious mistake. A child who has been abused needs special support and treatment as early as possible. The longer he continues to be abused or is left to deal with the situation on his own, the harder it is for children to be able to heal and develop optimally physically and mentally.

There are no behaviours that relate to a particular type of child abuse or neglect. Here is a short list of physical signs and behavioural changes in children who may have experienced abuse or neglect:

Physical Signs

- Any injury (bruise, burn, fracture, abdominal or head injury) that cannot be explained
- Failure to gain weight (especially in infants) or sudden dramatic weight gain
- Genital pain or bleeding
- A sexually transmitted disease

Other Changes that Should Raise Concern

- Fearful behaviour (nightmares, depression, unusual fears)
- Abdominal pain, bed-wetting (especially if the child has already been toilet trained)
- Attempts to run away
- Extreme sexual behaviour that seems inappropriate for the child's age
- Sudden change in self-confidence
- Headaches or stomachaches with no medical cause
- Abnormal fears, increased nightmares
- School failure
- Extremely passive or aggressive behaviour
- Desperately affectionate behaviour or social withdrawal
- Big appetite and stealing food

Preventing Abuse and Neglect

The major reasons for physical and psychological maltreatment of children within the family often are parental feelings of isolation, stress, and frustration. Parents need support and as much information as possible in order to raise their children responsibly. They need to be taught how to cope with their own feelings of frustration and anger without venting them on children. They also need the companionship of other adults who will listen and help during times of crisis.

Personal supervision of and involvement in your child's activities are the best ways to prevent physical and sexual abuse outside the home. Pay careful attention to your child's reports about and reactions to his experiences at child care and school. Always investigate if your child tells you he's been maltreated or if he undergoes a sudden unexplained change in behaviour.

Although you don't want to frighten your child, you can teach him some basic rules of safety in a non-threatening manner. Teach him to keep his distance from strangers, not to wander away from you in unfamiliar territory, to say “no” when someone asks him to do something against his will, and always to tell you if someone hurts him or makes him feel bad.

The Impact of Child Abuse and Neglect

i. Psychological issues

After spending their formative years in depression and anxiety, an individual is more likely to indulge in smoking, and alcohol and drug abuse. This can lead to physical health problems. Low self-esteem, depression, and relationship difficulties can arise from a childhood of abuse and neglect, as well as difficulties during infancy. Children who were abused at a young age commonly show signs of depression, and abuse and neglect can also cause psychological and emotional conditions such as panic disorder, dissociative disorders, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, depression, anger, posttraumatic stress disorder, and reactive attachment disorder. Low results in cognitive capacity, language development, and academic achievement are also seen in children placed in foster homes or out-of-home care.

ii. Physical health consequences

Psychological issues can result in a destructive streak among children. However, there are also immediate physical issues inflicted upon children, such as bruises, cuts, or broken bones. These can cause a lifetime of both physical and psychological issues. Victims of child abuse also suffer from higher incidence of allergies, arthritis, asthma, bronchitis, high blood pressure, and ulcers.

iii. Societal consequences

Child abuse and neglect touch across all aspects of development - personal, societal, and national. It hampers children’s survival, development and participation. Therefore, a mandate of child protection is essential, to ensure stability in children’s health, education and well-being, enabling them to contribute to society as future citizens. According to NGO Save the Children, ‘child protection’ is defined as a set of measures and structures to prevent and respond to abuse, neglect, violence and exploitation affecting children. Donate to NGO fundraising to ensure that every child, irrespective of their circumstances.

Conclusion

The NGO acts as a major key independent child protection body, and has extensive experience in partnering with civil society organisations, child-led initiatives, governments and other key stakeholders to stop all forms of violence against children. Its strong alliances with local governance enable the NGO to intervene in situations where child labour and abuse is suspected. It helps move survivors of child labour and abuse to rehabilitation, giving them medical care. It conducts regular raids to free child labour, and transitions these children to environmental that happier. It supports preschool to primary school transition to mainstream education. Donors to the NGO receive a substantial donation tax rebate, and the satisfaction that they’ve made a difference.

Web Sources

1. <https://www.savethechildren.in/resource-centre/articles/what-is-child-abuse-and-neglect>
2. <https://healthychildren.org/English/safety-prevention/at-home/Pages/What-to-Know-about-Child-Abuse.aspx>
3. <http://www.shemagazinepk.com/lifestyle/self/you-can-stop-child-abuse/>